

Neoliberal governmentality in global English textbooks

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to contribute to the growing body of literature critically analysing the relation between neoliberalism and the global English Language Teaching (ELT) textbook with a new perspective. In this study, neoliberalism is regarded not only as an economic policy paradigm, but especially in a Foucauldian way, as a form of governmentality, with its emphasis on the responsabilisation of the self and the creation of a certain kind of subjectivity, related to the entrepreneurial-consumerist concept of society. The corpus of the study consists of two best-selling global English textbooks published by prestigious academic publishers. I develop a quantitative analysis followed by a qualitative examination of the data to explore in which way and to what extent global English textbooks reflect, legitimate and reproduce neoliberal governmentality. The findings of the analysis suggest that the global ELT textbook not only presents a particular neoliberal worldview as common sense, but also encourages students to implement techniques of self-government to become entrepreneurial individuals and responsible consumers. In light of that, the paper concludes by arguing that the global ELT textbook may be regarded as a tool to enrich and support the expansion of neoliberal governmentality in today's society.

Keywords: neoliberalism; governmentality; English language teaching (ELT); textbook analysis; responsabilisation of the self

Introduction

For more than two decades, neoliberalism —the latest phase of capitalism— has been set as a key construct for critical studies not only in the field of economics, but also in the social sciences, and more recently as well in the areas of education (Giroux 2005; Hill and Kumar 2009) and applied linguistics (Block, Gray, and Holborow 2012; Duchêne and Heller 2012). In recent years, neoliberalism has also become the object of growing interest in the particular field of foreign language teaching and learning, as this realm is increasingly framed in economic terms. The impact of neoliberalism in language education is observable at different levels. The most evident neoliberal effect is the extended conception of language purely as a job skill or as a tool for future economic success (Kubota 2011; Shin 2016; Warriner 2016), without any communitarian component of national identity, and detachable from its speaker's social and cultural background. On the other hand, neoliberalism has also implicated the conversion of language teachers into 'expendable and replaceable knowledge workers' and of language learners into 'entrepreneurs and consumers' (Bernstein et al. 2015, 6–7). In this regard, Block and Gray (2016) discover the strong influence of neoliberalism in two English language teacher preparation programs, which emphasizes a highly instrumental notion of English and reinforces the 'de-skilling and discrediting' of language teachers (482).

Along these lines of investigation, the purpose of this paper is to explore the impact of neoliberalism on the global English Language Teaching (ELT) textbook, which continues to play a central role in most ELT classrooms all over the world. Most often, the textbook provides 'the basis for the syllabus, the springboard for other activities and discussions, guidance for new teachers, and socialization into the practice of language teaching and learning for students' (Chapelle 2016, 2). For the particular

case of the global ELT textbooks, some of their peculiarities discussed by Gray (2010) should be highlighted. They are normally produced by prestigious academic houses, and usually promoted with extended and aggressive advertising campaigns to compete with locally produced materials. They do not follow the curriculum requirements and standards of the ministries of education, although they are used both in private language schools and in the public education sector. And, above all, the global English textbook is a key component of the multi-billion-dollar profits that the ELT publishing industry generates globally.

The approach of this paper takes inspiration from a Critical Discourse Studies (CDS) framework, which examines ‘society through discourse, and contextualize[s] (and understand[s]) discourse through an analysis of its historical, socio-political and cultural foundations’ (Flowerdew and Richardson 2018, 2). With this in mind, I aim to explore how the neoliberal discourse is reproduced and legitimized in English textbooks for a global audience. My core focus is on the relation between the global ELT textbook and its broader political, social, economic and cultural context, which I define as neoliberal governmentality. By doing so, I aspire to understand the global English textbook in the light of an examination of today’s capitalism as a whole.

The paper begins with a brief review of research interests of critical studies about ELT textbooks, with a special emphasis on those studies which have situated neoliberalism within their focus. The following provides a description of the concept of governmentality to explain the understanding of neoliberalism in this paper. The next section presents the corpus of the study and outlines the methodological approach which is based on four main features of neoliberal governmentality. I then discuss the results of the quantitative and qualitative analysis of two currently widely used global ELT textbooks. I conclude the paper by considering the particular implications of my

findings for language teaching and learning, and suggesting future directions for research.

Critical research on ELT textbooks

Critical studies on ELT textbooks have been mainly focused on the representations of reality that these materials embody. At the beginning in the 1970s, critical research on ELT textbooks was concerned with gender issues with the objective to combat sexist representations (e.g. Hartman and Judd 1978; Porreca 1984). The focus was subsequently widened to include matters concerning race and ethnicity (e.g. Ndura 2004), sexual orientation (Gray 2013), and intercultural communication and multiculturalism (e.g. García 2005; Shin, Eslami, and Chen 2011). This entire body of research has succeeded to identify and, in many cases, has contributed to help eliminate the unfair portrayal of people in textbooks because of their gender, race, sexual orientation, or cultural and geographic origin. However, since the outbreak of the 2007-2008 global economic crisis, critical research on ELT textbooks is slowly moving from considerations about identity issues to a focus on the impact of neoliberalism on their content.

Gray (2010) was among the first authors to address neoliberal discourse in global ELT textbooks, showing that the representation of the world of work associated with self-branding coincides with the values and practices of neoliberalism. In another study, Gray (2012) signals the impact of neoliberalism in the rise of celebrities in English textbooks, characterized mainly by their wealth or by their business and professional success stories. Elsewhere, Gray and Block (2014) detect the progressive disappearance of characters and themes related to the working class in global English textbooks starting from the 1990s and coinciding with the rise of neoliberalism.

Similarly, Copley (2018) shows a great contrast between the focus on collective problems in textbooks from the 1970s and the individualistic emphasis in present-day neoliberal textbooks. Along these lines of investigation, Babaii and Sheikhi (2018) examine neoliberal traces in American and British ELT materials used in Iran, such as market mentality, individualism, competition, consumerism and branding. In a similar vein, Xiong and Yuan (2018) chose four excerpts from one of the most popular ELT series in China to uncover the neoliberal discourse.

This study aims to contribute to this growing body of research analysing neoliberal discourse in global textbooks from a new perspective. In this paper, neoliberalism is regarded not only as an economic policy paradigm, but especially as the rationality that shapes people's behaviour in western societies and beyond (Dardot and Laval 2013). For this reason, my critical discourse analysis is based on the concept of governmentality (Foucault 2008) to explain the discourse and practices featured in global ELT textbooks. In particular, I aim to capture how textbooks reflect and reproduce both the current macro social, economic and political climate, and particular individual conducts and perceptions. All of this will be framed within the construct of neoliberal governmentality, which is discussed in the next section.

Neoliberalism as governmentality

According to Foucault (2008), beyond a set of economic and social policies, neoliberalism should be regarded especially as a form of governmentality. This neologism captures Foucault's idea of the reciprocal relations between dominance and power over others (government) and forms of thoughts (mentality). Governmentality, often defined as the 'conduct of conduct' (Brown 2015, 117), explains how certain ways of thinking and behaving become considered as natural and proper at a certain time of

history due to the interplay between the actions of those who govern and of those who are governed. The point of those who rule is not to suppress the freedom of the governed but to guide their conduct by ‘arranging a certain space within which they will evolve’ (Laval 2018, 19). Neoliberalism, as governmentality, produces a political rationality that determines the ways governments manage people’s actions through technologies of domination and the ways people conduct their own behaviour through technologies of the self (Lemke 2002). In Foucauldian terms, technology refers to a set of practices that is oriented towards controlling the social and physical world through specific routines. The particular forms of the application of these technologies are known as techniques.

The main criterion of neoliberal rationality is not the absolute autonomy of the economy (*laissez-faire*) as it was within liberal rationality (Foucault 2008). Instead, the core of neoliberal governmentality serves to articulate the whole social body in accordance with the principle of competition in order to form a market society “made up of enterprise-units” (Foucault 2008, 225). In other words, all the segments of life are articulated in market terms, even those domains where money is not involved (Brown 2015, 31). In this regard, Dardot and Laval (2013, 3) argue that neoliberalism defines an ‘existential norm’ in Western societies and beyond, which ‘enjoins everyone to live in a world of generalized competition’.

Under neoliberal governmentality, each person thus has to become a new kind of *homo oeconomicus* (Brown 2015; Foucault 2008): the self-entrepreneurial, autonomous, and self-regulating individual, which embodies flexibility, self-branding, risk management and personal achievement. Individuals must assume ‘the duty of the self – its simultaneous responsabilisation as a moral agent and its construction as a calculative rational choice actor’ (Peters 2001, 61). As such, they must invest in themselves (in

education, health, security, etc.) to compete in a market society in order to maximize their profits at the expense of others. The so called ‘experts of subjectivity’ (Rose 1998, 151), such as personal therapists, consultants and career coaches, play an increasingly important role in the configuration of this neoliberal subjectivity, giving prescriptions for what should be done to manage the life of each individual.

As long as adequate skills and efforts are developed, individuals can become ‘the makers of their own fortune’ (Bay Cheng et al. 2015, 83). Accordingly, if some people are left behind, there are not structural injustices to explain their failure. It is only their own fault, because they have chosen passivity and inflexibility over the effort to work to improve themselves in order to provide for their own necessities. This understanding creates the general belief that we live in a meritocratic society, based on ‘the idea that whatever our social position at birth, society ought to offer enough opportunity and mobility for ‘talent’ to combine with ‘effort’ in order to ‘rise to the top’ (Littler 2013, 52).

The glorification of self-entrepreneurs in today’s society can be seen, for example, in the rise of TV programs that turn entrepreneurs into celebrities, many of which later use the popularity television gave them to secure their political interests and ideas (Boyle and Kelly 2010). Together with the self-entrepreneur, the consumer is the other hegemonic model of subjectivity in this new market-driven society. For Bauman (2007, 55), in the society of consumers where we now live ‘*everyone* needs to be, ought to be, must be a consumer-by-vocation’ (italics in the original), and that is a ‘human right and universal human duty that knows of no exception’. In this respect, Foucault (2008, 226) argues that the neoliberal consumer should not be regarded simply as someone who buys a product, but as an entrepreneur who produces his own satisfaction insofar as he consumes.

Another key element of neoliberal governmentality is personal and corporate social responsibility. On the one hand, individuals are not only responsible for their own faith, but should also try to help to improve the distortions made by the capitalist society by protecting the environment or by making smart, responsible consumer choices (Castro 2015, 283). As promoted by the World Economic Forum in Davos—one of the most important neoliberal capitalist think tanks—, consumers should conceive themselves as moral actors with the responsibility to improve the world (Giesler and Veseriu 2014). The companies, on the other hand, should create a corporative conscience, which means assuming moral values that go beyond pure self-interest (Shamir 2008). Competition, self-interest and economic rationality are still the driving principles of corporations, but they are combined with ‘corporate social responsibility, continuing education, ethical consumption or charitable contributions to lend capitalism a “human face”’ (Vrasti 2011, 3). All of this entails that, according to neoliberal governmentality, individuals, civic organizations and corporations should assume duties regarding collective issues previously assigned to the state, such as welfare, occupation, health, and environmental protection.

Methodology

I collected data from two global English textbooks for adults currently widely used all over the world: *Face2Face/Pre-Intermediate* (2nd edition) published by Cambridge University Press (Redston and Cunningham 2012), and *New Headway/Upper-Intermediate* (4th edition), published by Oxford University Press (Soars and Soars 2014). The selection of this sample of textbooks was based on the fact that they are published by two of the biggest publishing houses of ELT materials. Therefore, both textbooks are outstanding representatives of the very lucrative global English language

industry, in which the global ELT textbook is an essential component (Gray 2010). In addition, I decided to choose textbooks from two different levels to provide a more complete picture of the issue. Along with the student's book, I also reviewed the accompanying workbook as it contains relevant data for the analysis.

My analytical procedures are derived from the fundamental principles of CDS, whose central aim has been exploring the interrelationship between discourse and its social, cultural, political and economic context (Fairclough and Wodak 1997). Rather than being a unique method for discourse analysis, CDS brings together a variety of perspectives and approaches with a shared interest to issues of power and inequality (Van Dijk 2009). For the purpose of this study, I adopted a methodology similar to the one developed for the content analysis of language textbooks in other studies (Bori and Petanović 2016; Gray 2010). An initial quantitative analysis is followed by a qualitative examination of the data which considers how discourse in textbooks reproduces broader social, economic and political trends in society and, at the same time, how discourse shapes these dominant trends.

The analysis is based on my readings on neoliberal governmentality, which was explained in the previous section. Based on my literature review about this topic, I elaborated a pool of four items that encapsulate the main features of neoliberal governmentality: competition, consumerism, personal and corporate social responsibility, and self-entrepreneurship (which itself includes flexibility, self-branding, risk management and personal achievement). I begin the analysis by counting the number of units in each textbook which contain practices or values related to any of these four main neoliberal features. Later, in the qualitative analysis, I examine the discursive forms that these neoliberal values and practices adopt in textbooks. To achieve this, as I did in a recent study about language textbooks (Author), I take into

consideration: (a) the voices of the authors and characters of texts (their experiences and the outcomes explained); (b) the activities proposed for students by textbooks; and (c) the visual content (pictures and drawings). In that way, I am able to identify the set of ideas that textbooks use discursively to create meanings about the world. Moreover, in view of the activities proposed, the student conduct promoted by textbooks is also recognized.

Results and discussion

Quantitative analysis

As can be seen in Table 1, all the units in the corpus, with the exception of one unit in each textbook, include content related to one or more of the four items that encapsulate neoliberal governmentality. This content occurs in oral and written texts, pictures, and also in the activities for the students. Even though each of these four neoliberal items can be identified separately, they are clearly connected. A story about a self-entrepreneur may be associated with the personal responsibility of this individual, and his desire to distinguish himself from his competitors is a clear signal of competition. As a result, in some units the occurrence of only one of these neoliberal items was identified, while in other units several neoliberal features appear altogether.

[INSERT TABLE 1 HERE]

Although the results of the quantitative analysis give a general overview of the frequency of neoliberal practices and values within both textbooks, it is necessary to look more carefully into some of these occurrences to have a better understanding of how textbooks embody neoliberal rationality. For this reason, the following qualitative

analysis will give more detail about the items of neoliberal governmentality identified in the quantitative analysis. In the first part of the qualitative examination of the data we shall see multiple examples of self-entrepreneurship, which go together with individual achievement and economic success, innovation, competition and the belief in the fairness of a meritocratic society. Subsequently, we will also see examples of consumerism, environmental mastery and charity, related to personal and corporate social responsibility.

Creating self-entrepreneurs

There is a lot of business-related content in both the textbooks analysed. In many texts, pictures and activities, famous entrepreneurs appear as central figures. There are, for example, two entire pages dedicated to the founders of Apple and Starbucks (Soars and Soars 2014, 50-1). Personal achievement, competition, and innovation are the main features of this content. Although Steve Jobs designed his first computer in his bedroom, he ultimately found a way to compete with Microsoft. His story is not just a story of success or technological advancement. Apple's products have something special, as the text explains: They are 'beautifully stylish products' that 'have changed the way the world reads, watches, listens and communicates'. On the other hand, Howard Schultz —the owner of Starbucks— is a classical kind of capitalist businessman who took over a small company, transformed it to suit the needs of a greater public and is 'currently worth \$13 billion'. Famous businessmen like Jobs and Shultz have appeared in ELT textbooks since the 1990s (Gray 2012). They are the so-called achieved celebrities, whose success is the result of some kind of merit. As Littler (2013, 55) rightly states, this discourse of neoliberal meritocracy functions 'as an ideological myth to *obscure* economic and social inequalities' (italics in the original).

As a matter of fact, it could be frustrating for many English learners since social mobility is a distant possibility for the majority of people in the world in which the division between the rich and poor is getting higher by the day.

In the activities following this content, students are first asked to explain why these brands become successful or what makes them special. Later, they are encouraged to put into practice their entrepreneurial spirit, imagining that they are going to open a restaurant. Working in small groups, they are to discuss details of this initiative (how to get money to start, types of advertisement, number of workers employed, etc.), present the business plan in front of the class and, finally, discuss the development of the enterprise, if it becomes successful, by answering the three following questions: ‘Should you raise prices?’; ‘Should you expand?’; ‘The economy enters a recession and business slows. What do you do to stay profitable?’ (Soars and Soars 2014, 52). Hence, after presenting worldly famous entrepreneurial initiatives, the textbook provides instructions on how to behave in the business world in order to become successful self-entrepreneurs. More than that of language learning material, this kind of content resembles that found in any of the numerous step-by-step guides to start a successful business. Following the general trends of neoliberal governmentality, the textbook emphasizes ‘self-empowerment’ (Peters 2001, 62), through the encouragement of such content and instructions to better develop personal skills which would supposedly help students if and when they decided to start their own business.

Along the same lines, both global textbooks choose to show students the life of the world-famous chef Jamie Oliver, another representative of an achieved kind of celebrity. Together with his overwhelming success, *Face2Face* emphasizes the good he has done for the community, with his campaign to supply children with healthier food in schools (Redston and Cunningham 2012, 6). In the questions related to the reading

comprehension of the text, students are asked to look again at this point, explaining why Oliver conducted this campaign and how this influenced the British government to spend extra money on school meals. Oliver's story here resurges as an example of yet another neoliberal characteristic, that is, the increasingly symbiotic relationship between business celebrities and the governments (Boyle and Kelly 2010). This famous chef, working together with politicians in power, is one among many celebrity entrepreneurs that has contributed to shaping government's policies of a business model of society, and helping it to become a mainstream discourse of education, entering schools and classrooms (Boyle and Kelly 2010).

The texts and pictures of Jamie Oliver in *New Headway* are followed by activities related to ethical topics such as fair-trade and organic food (Soars and Soars 2014, 110-11). The textbook first presents the reading of a consumer report by the Organic Burger Company. Then, students are to imagine themselves as marketing consultants to explore whether shoppers are ready to buy more fair-trade products. In particular, learners are asked to carry out a consumer survey about this topic and to write a report. In other words, not only are students put in a business-like situation, but they are encouraged to become propagators of organic, fair-trade products. From a governmentality point of view, it can be seen that textbooks not only create meanings about entrepreneurship and its corporate social responsibility, but also guide the conduct the learners should follow. It is an example of what Laval (2018, 16) calls a 'a performative discourse, which in guise of describing what is, dictates what must be done to make it so'.

Another way of giving support to different kinds of entrepreneurial efforts is seen in a listening activity about young people who paint ads of private companies on their faces and heads (Soars and Soars 2014, 49). In the photograph following the

activity, we can see three young men smiling with their faces and heads painted with advertisements. One of these characters has a painted slogan saying *Buy my Face*. The branding of individuals for marketing and advertising purposes is nothing new. In neoliberal times ‘everything either is for sale or is plundered for profit’ (Giroux 2005, 77). Even our own bodies are commercially available on the market, and the textbook encourages this. In the listening activity, this behaviour is presented as a good business opportunity, and the textbook does not question this rather perverse practice in which intimate spaces such as body parts are transformed to places of profit. In the following activity, students are again asked to put this content into practice. After talking about adverts they like, they are to devise their own advert for a product or service of their choice.

All characters in the textbooks who work embody some of the main features of the self-entrepreneur. There is, for example, a listening exercise about an office assistant who shows her absolute flexibility to get involved in multitasking and in the 24/7 work culture (Redston and Cunningham 2012, 28). When her boss asks her about the delay in her report, she apologizes and promises to send it immediately. She also agrees to take nine clients out to dinner and entertain them, although she has to cancel an appointment with her boyfriend. In other words, work comes first, at any hour and at the cost of one’s personal life. Under this business context, students are then to practice structures to express apologies, reasons and promises. Stated another way, they are exposed to these linguistic structures while at the same time they are introduced to a kind of labour flexibility that Bauman (2007, 7) defines as ‘zero-drag’, meaning that the employee is always available to accept additional tasks and emergency calls, or even to change where he or she works, without any obstacles or complaints.

When unemployed characters appear in textbooks, they always end up finding a new job. For example, Harry is a 54-year old man that worked for an engineering company for 17 years until it closed down (Redston and Cunningham 2012, 24). He complains about not being given a chance to find a new job because of his age. In another text in the same unit, everything turns out well for Harry as he gets a job as car parts salesman. Harry is a symbol of many unfortunate unemployed people who get fired some years before their retirement. In the text, Harry is also an exemplary representation of the neoliberal subject – he is not complaining about the systemic failures of the society, he is being persistent and pro-active and, in the end, it pays off. Unfortunately, this is not the case for many people in the real world. Textbooks tend to neglect addressing the crucial issues, the reasons behind the lay-offs: businesses closing down, but most importantly the lack of systemic protection for the unemployed. They portray a reality in which it seems that there is no institutional responsibility or structural inequality. It all comes down to personal responsibility. And the textbooks prove to be a guide into practices of how to handle the current competitive and flexible labour market. Not only do they teach students how to interpret job advertisements, to write CVs and motivational and cover letters and to prepare for a job interview, but they also include expert knowledge in texts such as the one titled ‘Top tips for finding a new job’ (Tims, Redston and Cunningham 2012, 17). In that way, textbook authors become ‘experts of subjectivity’ (Rose 1998) who aim to regulate the conduct of the population with their advice (in this case, for finding employment). Once again, we see students conceived as ‘responsibilised individuals’, who are ‘called upon to apply certain management, economic, and actuarial techniques to themselves as subjects’ (Peters 2001, 70), in order to behave appropriately in a market-driven society.

Consumerism and responsibility in the spotlight

Consumerism is a regular and core item in global ELT textbooks. However, the consumer aspect of textbooks is not just reserved for buying products at the supermarket. Even when treating topics such as education, culture or work, consumerism and consumer related practices are placed in the foreground. The material aspect of people's lives is emphasized with texts and photos about buying and selling commodities, ranging from clothes, appliances and houses to movies, concerts and travel arrangements, including student loans, even about the selling of Britney Spear's used chewing gum. Almost everything existent in textbooks is treated from the point of view of the market. Students are encouraged and even taught to be consumers, and, as such, to freely enjoy a wide variety of products and services, and also to fight for their rights as consumers if something goes wrong. In both textbooks, for example, there are activities to learn how to write a letter of complaint. They are accompanied by sample letters of customers who complain about traveling and tourism matters. In Foucauldian terms, activities to learn how to write a letter of complaint should be understood as techniques that textbooks provide to students for shaping their social practices and, in that way, regulate themselves as self-reliable consumers. The process of learning the exact procedures in which to respond to consumer-related situations comes from the neoliberal logic that citizens are rational actors who should adopt appropriate linguistic tools in order to successfully act in economic transactions on their own. This production of responsible consumers has the ultimate goal of freeing the state and corporations of responsibility (Castro 2015).

Learners in textbooks are also guided on how to be responsible when managing their money as consumers, by means of the advice an expert gives to negotiate with companies to get 'rock-bottom prices' (Soars, Soars and McCaul 2014, 41). After being

exposed to expert knowledge about money-related matters, students are encouraged to learn specialized vocabulary about this topic and use words such as ‘bargains’, ‘haggle’ and ‘pay off’ in a fill-in-the gap activity. This kind of activity fits very well within the proposal of one of the main responsible consumer subjects that needed be created according to the World Economic Forum in Davos — the financially literate consumer (Giesler and Veresiu, 2014).

The topic of corporate social responsibility regarding planetary problems is also present in textbooks. There are a few mentions of companies being socially responsible. For example, learners are informed that every year the multinational Ben and Jerry’s gives ‘7.5% of the company’s money to charity’ (Tims, Redston and Cunningham 2012, 10-11). In the follow-up activity, students are asked to explain the reason for the opening of their foundation, which is, as the textbook explains, to help poor people. Similarly, the text about the coffee chain Starbucks says that it has a ‘company policy of fair trade and employee welfare’ (Soars and Soars 2014, 51). With this kind of content, textbooks legitimize and promote the discourse of the so called ‘philanthropic capitalists’ who present their public personas and enterprises according to the good they do for the society (charity, investments into welfare, education, poor countries) rather than to the fact that these companies are being ferociously competitive (Vrasti 2011).

Finally, it is also worth commenting in some detail on the content dedicated to animal protection and to the organization of charity events in *Face2Face* (Redston and Cunningham 2012, 42-5). The textbook first presents a two-page text that explains that, with the help of organizations such as the World Wide Fund (WWF), gorillas are being saved from extinction. It is also argued that the tourist industry helps the animal preservation, as it generates economic profits that incentivize local people to protect gorillas and their habitats. Learners are then to put this content into practice by firstly

thinking about five ways they can help the environment and animals. In the next activity, there is a listening exercise of British people who are planning a charity event for the WWF. In the photograph, they are all elegantly dressed businessmen and women. After practicing some structures (asking questions, making offers and suggestions), students are encouraged to decide on a charity event, and in groups of four organize it. In all these texts and practices of self-responsibilisation, there is a clear bond between the responsible, action-oriented, rational subjects and civil or non-governmental organizations. Market logic also lures from the sidelines of these practices and narratives. The ‘good’, socially and ethically responsible corporations, the tourist industry and its commercial side are apostrophized as inevitable for the protection of the environment. In accordance to neoliberal governmentality, therefore, the state has been exempted from any political intervention in these social questions (Dardot and Laval 2013).

Conclusions

The critical analysis of this paper has revealed that the discourse of global ELT textbooks is constructed in a way congruent to the main principles of neoliberal governmentality. Narratives in these language teaching materials stress a particular vision of the reality, impregnated by the benefits of entrepreneurship, self-responsibilisation and corporate social responsibility, as well as the pleasures of consumption. Textbooks present this particular representation of the world as the way things really are, as natural and obvious, making it common sense, without reference to questions related to the structural inequality of the current economic and political capitalist system. Furthermore, the activities in textbooks focus on the development of entrepreneurial, job-seeking and consumer skills rather than on critical awareness,

reflection and dialogue. Across a range of activities, students in textbooks are encouraged to adopt different techniques of self-government to learn how to become entrepreneurial individuals and responsible consumers.

In recent years, especially with the outburst of the global economic crises in 2007-2008, the focus of several ELT textbook analyses turns to neoliberalism as a key factor in shaping the present and the future of language education. However, ELT textbooks have not been previously analysed through the lens of neoliberal governmentality, with its ‘emphasis on the question of how *power* is exercised’ (Peters 2001, 67; italics in the original). The focus on neoliberal governmentality in this paper offers some unique insights for a better understanding of the current global ELT textbook. The findings discussed above suggest that textbooks not only inscribe certain meanings to the language taught, but also take a leading role in guiding the conduct of students to shape the construction of a neoliberal subjectivity. ELT textbooks thus emerge as instruments for the governing of learners’ souls in accordance to free-market economic values and practices. In this context, ELT textbooks may contribute to the internalisation of these ideals and behaviours within students and to implement this neoliberal rationality in relation to themselves and to others. This is precisely what enhances the impact of neoliberal governmentality. It is not necessary to be established as a norm. Everybody reproduces the neoliberal rationality in a way that this power ends up being inside each of us (Dardot and Laval 2013).

Obviously, it will largely depend on each teacher and on each group of students in what way these ELT textbooks impregnated with neoliberal governmentality are articulated in the classroom. This paper aspires to be a valuable source for education professionals to become aware of the neoliberal nature of language textbooks and to take measures to challenge in the classroom the growing neoliberal common sense in

language teaching and learning (Bernstein et al. 2015). In my opinion, critical thinking and questioning of textbooks' neoliberal content could be beneficial to enrich both pedagogical practices and educational outcomes. Besides, only through a critical attitude towards commercial ELT textbooks, can students and teachers avoid becoming unwilling accomplices of the far-reaching effects of neoliberal rationality in today's society. However, further research is needed to explore how neoliberal ELT textbooks do actually affect the worldview of students and teachers, and especially to what extent their conduct is transformed. In particular, ethnographic case studies on ELT classrooms in different parts of the world would be necessary to assess to what degree neoliberal governmentality in global textbooks is either reproduced or rejected and resisted.

References

- Babaii, E., and M. Sheikhi 2018. "Traces of neoliberalism in English teaching materials: a critical discourse analysis." *Critical Discourse Studies* 15 (3): 247-64.
- Bauman, Z. 2007. *Consuming Life*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Bay-Cheng, L. Y., C.. Fitz, N.M. Alizaga, and A.N. Zucker. 2015. "Tracking homo oeconomicus: development of the neoliberal beliefs inventory." *Journal of Social and Political Psychology* 3: 71–88.
- Bernstein, K.A., E.A Hellmich, N. Katznelson, J. Shin, and K. Vinall, K. 2015. "Introduction to special issue: critical perspectives on neoliberalism in second/foreign language education." *L2 Journal* 7 (3): 3–14.
- Block, D. and J. Gray. 2016. "'Just go away and do it and you get marks': The degradation of language teaching in neoliberal times." *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development* 37 (5): 481–94.
- Block, D., J. Gray, and M. Holborow. 2012. *Neoliberalism and Applied Linguistics*. London: Routledge.
- Bori, P., and J. Petanović. 2016. "Constructing the entrepreneurial-self: how Catalan textbooks present the neoliberal worker to their students." *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies* 14 (3): 154–74.
- Boyle, R., and L. Kelly. 2010. "The celebrity entrepreneur on television: profile, politics and power." *Celebrity Studies* 1 (3): 334-50.
- Brown, W. 2015. *Undoing the Demos: Neoliberalism's Stealth Revolution*. New York: Zone Books.
- Castro, J.C.L. 2015. "The consumer as agent in neoliberalism." *Matrizes* 9 (2): 273-88.
- Chapelle, C.A. 2016. *Teaching Culture in Introductory Foreign Language Textbooks*. Basingstoke: Palgrave.

- Copley, K. 2018. "Neoliberalism and ELT coursebook content." *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies* 15 (1): 43-62.
- Dardot, P., and C. Laval. 2013. *The New Way of the World: On Neoliberal Society*. London: Verso Books.
- Duchêne, A., and M. Heller. 2012. *Language in Late Capitalism: Pride and Profit*. London: Routledge.
- Fairclough, N., and R. Wodak. 1997. "Critical discourse analysis." In *Discourse as a Social Interaction*, edited by T.A. Van Dijk, 258–84. London: Sage.
- Flowerdew, J., and J. Richardson. 2018. "Introduction." In *The Routledge Handbook of Critical Discourse Studies*, edited by J. Flowerdew and J. Richardson, 1–10. London: Routledge.
- Foucault, M. 2008. *The Birth of Biopolitics: Lectures at the Collège de France, 1978–1979*. Basingstoke: Palgrave.
- García, M.C.M. 2005. "International and intercultural issues in English teaching textbooks: the case of Spain." *Intercultural Education* 16 (1): 57-68.
- Giesler, M., and E. Veresiu. 2014. "Creating the responsible consumer: moralistic governance regimes and consumer subjectivity." *Journal of Consumer Research* 41(3): 840-57.
- Giroux, H. 2005. "Cultural studies in dark times: public pedagogy and the challenge of neoliberalism." *Fast Capitalism* 1 (2): 75-86.
- Gray, J. 2010. "The branding of English and the culture of the new capitalism: representations of the world of work in English language textbooks." *Applied Linguistics* 31 (5): 714–33.
- Gray, J. 2012. "Neoliberalism, celebrity and 'aspirational content' in English language teaching textbooks for the global market." In *Neoliberalism and Applied*

- Linguistics*, edited by D. Block, J. Gray, and M. Holborow, 86–113. London: Routledge.
- Gray, J. 2013. “LGBT invisibility and heteronormativity in ELT materials.” In *Critical Perspectives on Language Teaching Materials*, edited by J. Gray, 40–63. Basingstoke: Palgrave.
- Gray, J., and D. Block 2014. “All middle class now? Evolving representations of the working class in the neoliberal era: the case of ELT textbooks.” In *English Language Teaching Textbook*, edited by N. Harwood, 45–71. Basingstoke: Palgrave.
- Hartman, P.L., and E.L Judd. 1978. “Sexism and TESOL materials.” *TESOL Quarterly* 12: 383–93.
- Hill, D., and R. Kumar, eds. 2009. *Global Neoliberalism and Education and its Consequences*. London: Routledge.
- Kubota, R. 2011. “Questioning linguistic instrumentalism: English, neoliberalism, and language tests in Japan.” *Linguistics and Education* 22 (3): 248–60.
- Laval, C. 2018. “May ’68: Paving the way for the triumph of neoliberalism? Rereading the event with Foucault and Bourdieu.” *La Deleuziana* 8: 9-27.
- Lemke, T. 2002. “Foucault, Governmentality, and Critique.” *Rethinking Marxism: A Journal of Economics, Culture & Society* 14 (3): 49-64.
- Littler, J. 2013. “Meritocracy as plutocracy: the marketising of “equality” within neoliberalism.” *New Formations: a journal of culture/theory/politics* 80-81: 52-72.
- Ndura, E. 2004. “ESL and cultural bias: an analysis of elementary through high school textbooks in the Western United States of America.” *Language, Culture and Curriculum* 17: 143–53.
- Peters, M. 2001. “Education, enterprise culture and the entrepreneurial self: a Foucauldian perspective.” *Journal of Educational Enquiry* 2 (2): 58-71.

- Porreca, K.L. 1984. "Sexism in current ESL textbooks." *TESOL Quarterly* 18: 704–24.
- Redston, C., and G. Cunningham. 2012. *Face2Face/Pre-Intermediate. Student's Book* (2nd edition). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Rose, N. 1998. *Inventing ourselves: Psychology, Power, and Personhood*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Shamir, R. 2008. "The age of responsabilization: on market-embedded morality." *Economy and Society* 37 (1): 1-19.
- Shin, H. 2016. "Language 'skills' and the neoliberal English education industry." *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development* 37 (5): 509–22.
- Shin, J., Z. Eslami, and W.C. Chen. 2011. "Presentation of local and international culture in current international English-language teaching textbooks." *Language, Culture and Curriculum* 24 (3): 253-68.
- Soars, J., and L. Soars. 2014. *New Headway/Upper-Intermediate. Student's Book* (4th edition). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Soars, J., L. Soars, and J. McCaul. 2014. *New Headway/Upper-Intermediate. Workbook with Key* (4th edition). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Tims, N., C. Redston, and G. Cunningham. 2012. *Face2Face/Pre-Intermediate. Workbook*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Van Dijk, T.A. 2009. "Critical discourse studies: A sociocognitive approach." In *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis*, edited by R. Wodak and M. Meyer, 62-85. London: Sage.
- Vrasti, W. 2011. "'Caring' capitalism and the duplicity of critique." *Theory & Event* 14: 1–14
- Warriner, D.S. 2016. "'Here, without English, you are dead': ideologies of language and discourses of neoliberalism in adult English language learning." *Journal of*

Multilingual and Multicultural Development 37 (5): 495–508.

Xiong, T., and Z.M. Yuan. 2018. “‘It Was Because I Could Speak English That I Got the Job’: neoliberal discourse in a Chinese English textbook series.” *Journal of Language, Identity & Education* 17 (2): 103-17.

Table 1. Occurrences of neoliberal governmentality in textbooks

	<i>Face2Face</i>	<i>New Headway</i>	Total
Total number of units	12	12	24
Number of units with content related to neoliberal governmentality	11	11	22
Number of units related to competition	3	4	7
Number of units related to consumerism	4	5	9
Number of units related to personal and corporative social responsibility	5	4	9
Number of units related to self-entrepreneurship	8	7	15